

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DEONTOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN THE DAILY PRACTICE OF A DENTIST

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Abstract

Most researchers believe that for the optimal implementation of the principles of medical deontology, it is necessary to take into account a number of conditions: vocation, tact, intelligence, compliance with the norms of the doctor-patient relationship. According to some scientists, medical ethics also provides for a wide range of relationships between medical workers and patients, their relatives, and team members. Thus, it can be noted that medical ethics is identified with medical deontology. If the content of medical deontology is aimed at establishing the duty and duties of a doctor, then the content of the principles of bioethics is aimed at protecting the patient. Bioethics, as an integral part of pedagogy, defines the doctrine of the social, legal and ethical consequences of biomedical technology. The question is indisputable that a medical worker should always remember the patient, have the ability to "conquer and subjugate the soul of the patient". But not everyone agrees that the doctor's duty is to reassure the patient and convince him of the rationality of the chosen method of treatment, and the doctor must be friendly with the patient, show sincere interest in the problem, listen and analyze complaints, because the doctor and the patient have one goal - achieve recovery. The importance of applying the principles of bioethics in dentistry is explained, first of all, by the general significance of this area of medical knowledge and activity. **The aim of the research** was to study the level of awareness of young specialists - interns about ethical and bioethical issues at the stages of training and using knowledge in the future practice of dentists. **Materials and methods.** We have applied the method of active discussion about the expediency, role, place and importance of ethical and bioethical issues in the practice of dentists for the development of a competitive specialist. 58 dentists-interns were attended by the discussion (the first research group - 29 interns with an average diploma score of 4.65-5.0; the second group - 17 interns with an average diploma score of 4.0-4.6; the third group - 12 interns with an average diploma score of 3.5-3.9 and the result of "Krok-2 and Krok-3. Stomatology" 75-80.0%, which corresponds to the criterion "satisfactory"). **Conclusions.** Thus, in the process of research discussion in all three groups of interns-stomatologists, a common opinion was formed about the high relevance of ethical and bioethical issues in the practice of a dentist, as well as the role of such knowledge and skills in strengthening the competitiveness of future specialists.

Keywords: bioethics, deontology, pedagogy, dentistry.

Relevance. It is known that pedagogy is a social science that studies organized, systematic and purposeful activities for the formation of a person's personality; a science that studies the content, forms and methods of education, as well as the process of transferring experience to a student by a teacher. Pedagogy uses the following research methods: a) methods of forming the consciousness of the individual (persuasion): story, explanation, explanation, lecture, conversation, briefing,

dispute, report, example; b) methods of organizing activities and forming the experience of behavior: accustoming, pedagogical requirement, public opinion, educating situations; c) methods of stimulating behavior and activity (motivation): competition, encouragement.

Recently, more attention has been paid to interactive methods, such as the method of brainstorming, competitive groups, round tables, etc., but they do not fully cover the issues of medical ethics and bioethics,

and are often controversial and controversial [4, 13]. However, not only in Ukraine, but also in the countries of Europe, Asia and America, the study of medical ethics and bioethics as an integral part of pedagogy, in our opinion, is appropriate, important and essential for the development of thinking in the formation of a competitive doctor.

The term "deontology" (from the Greek words "*deontos*" due and "*logos*" - teaching) was introduced at the beginning of the last century by the English philosopher Bentham as the name of the science of professional human behavior. A part of general deontology is medical deontology, which studies the principles of behavior of medical personnel aimed at maximizing the usefulness of treatment and eliminating adversely affecting omissions in medical practice. The concept of medical deontology also includes a system of relationships that is established in the course of treatment between a doctor and a patient. In a narrow sense, medical deontology is a set of specific norms and principles of medical morality regarding a particular specialty. Deontology, being a part of medical ethics and morality and consisting of the principles of behavior of a medical worker in the performance of his professional duties, confirms the need to study it [5].

It is necessary that the principles, rules of ethics and deontology in the work of a physician become the subject of constant attention. In our opinion, it is this approach that should become the subject of constant attention of such a pedagogical approach. Taking into account that medical ethics and medical deontology focus on the role of moral principles and moral norms, principles and rules of conduct based on them, it is more correct to consider medical ethics and deontology in their unity.

Most researchers tend to believe that for the optimal implementation of the principles of medical deontology, it is necessary to take into account a number of conditions: vocation, tact, intelligence, compliance with the norms of the doctor-patient relationship [6, 7]. According to some scientists, medical ethics also provides for a wide range of relationships between medical workers and patients, their relatives, and team members. Thus, it can be noted that medical ethics is identified with medical deontology. If the content of medical deontology is aimed at establishing the duty and duties of a doctor, then the content of the principles of bioethics is aimed at protecting the patient [8, 9, 10]. Bioethics, as an integral part of pedagogy, defines the doctrine of the social, legal and ethical consequences of biomedical technology. The question is indisputable that a medical worker should always remember the patient, have the ability to "conquer and subjugate the soul of the patient" [11, 12].

But not everyone agrees that the doctor's duty is to reassure the patient and convince him of the rationality of the chosen method of treatment, and the doctor must be friendly with the patient, show sincere interest in the problem, listen and analyze complaints, because the doctor and the patient have one goal - achieve recovery [2, 4, 14]. Although many prominent scientists insist that the doctor needs to remember that he is dealing with people who deserve the most courteous and caring

attention [5, 7, 11, 13]. The importance of applying the principles of bioethics in dentistry is explained, first of all, by the general significance of this area of medical knowledge and activity.

In this regard, **the aim of the research** was to study the level of awareness of young specialists - interns about ethical and bioethical issues at the stages of training and using knowledge in the future practice of dentists.

Materials and methods. We have applied the method of active discussion about the expediency, role, place and importance of ethical and bioethical issues in the practice of dentists for the development of a competitive specialist.

58 dentists-interns were attended by the discussion. The first research group consisted of 29 interns with an average diploma score of 4.65-5.0, who passed the integrated licensed exam "License integrated exam Krok-2. Stomatology" with a score above 85%, which corresponds to the "excellent" criterion, and at the stage of postgraduate education they wrote the "License integrated exam Krok-3. Stomatology" with a score of over 89.0%. The second group consisted of 17 interns with an average diploma score of 4.0-4.6, the result of "License integrated exam Krok-2. Stomatology" and "License integrated exam Krok-3. Stomatology" 81.0-85.0%, which corresponds to the "good" criterion. The third group included 12 interns with an average diploma score of 3.5-3.9 and the result of "Krok-2 and Krok-3. Stomatology" 75-80.0%, which corresponds to the criterion "satisfactory".

Research results. All participants in the study from the 1st group (100%) showed deep knowledge of ethical and bioethical issues in the daily practice of a dentist, indicated the relationship of ethics as an integral part of pedagogy with the practical activities of a dentist, actively participated in the discussion, expressed interest in these important questions. It should be noted that, contrary to expectations, in the presence of sufficiently high performance indicators both at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels of education, 12 out of 17 (76%) persons of the 2nd group revealed nihilistic moods to participate in the discussion of the discussion topic. At the same time, all the interns included in the 3rd group were reluctant to enter into a discussion, were shy, and ultimately expressed the opinion that there is no need to apply ethical and bioethical standards in the daily practice of a doctor. Special attention, in our opinion, deserves the fact that it was in these groups of interns, where initially there were elements of unstable assessment results, which resulted in average and low results of academic progress both at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels, there was also a lack of self-assessment of the individual, which does not allow to freely discuss professional topics, probably potentiated by the lack of special knowledge, and the lack of a deontological position of the doctor's personality formed in the process of training, as a result of an ineffective pedagogical process.

At the same time, we note that after the end of the discussion, the opinion of all the interns who doubted the need to study ethical and bioethical norms changed

- they expressed a significant interest in ethical and bioethical issues, as well as a desire to obtain additional information about the ethical and bioethical norms of a doctor.

Conclusions. Thus, in the process of research discussion in all three groups of interns-stomatologists, a common opinion was formed about the high relevance of ethical and bioethical issues in the practice of a dentist, as well as the role of such knowledge and skills in strengthening the competitiveness of future specialists.

An analytical review of the literature showed that, to date, the ethical issues of the relationship of the patient (and / or his relatives) with the medical staff of the medical institution are not sufficiently covered in the specialized literature and are not fully represented in educational programs. Modern medicine requires the physician to be a well-educated person with a high cultural level and with a range of knowledge that goes beyond his specialty. Dental theory and practice are especially sensitive to the perception of the norms and principles of bioethics, since they deal with all categories of the population and are closely related to all other areas of medicine. Doctors - dentists should have a broad outlook, be versatile educated, thinking, be attentive and cordial towards patients. We are confident that in the activities of a dentist, moral and ethical principles should be embodied in a set of specific behavioral norms, the conscientious implementation of which will be both a professional duty for him and a matter of his professional honor and dignity.

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